

Educational Policy: Understanding Tri Pusat Pendidikan (Education Centers) as Efforts to Reach Educational Objectives

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ABSTRACT

This paper seeks to offer an interpretation of the significance of the core of education in an attempt to achieve public policy goals. Some publications addressing approaches, techniques, and models of learning as a means of understanding the ideal education, but there are still deficiencies attributable to educators or adults who do not see the environment as a place of training. The paper aims to provide parents, teachers, and the community with knowledge so that education is a joint obligation so that cooperation in the education system is complete. "Tri Pusat Pendidikan" are three critical elements that play an essential role in learning and become the center of educational activities, namely family education (informal education), school training (formal education), and social education (non-formal culture). The "Tri Pusat Pendidikan" idea means that learning can be done anywhere and at any time, being a mutual obligation. This principle says the society and family have a balanced responsibility for the success of education offenders, and that it is not just schools that are made and regulated as organizations that have a great (full) responsibility for the success of individuals in their educational cycle.

INTRODUCTION

Learning is an essential activity for human beings and plays a very strategic role as information is often developed about the progress and development of growth in any field. Quality of education is accepted when the teaching and learning process can operate efficiently, effectively, and the components of the system engage with the educational policy objectives, teachers, students, educational personnel, learning strategies, media, and assessment (Hamalik, 2003). Therefore, the quality of education can be seen in the learning outcomes displayed by students. Student learning outcomes are not entirely influenced by internal factors (physical, psychological, fatigue), but other factors contribute to the low or high student learning outcomes; these factors are external factors. Slameto believes that the factors that influence learning can be classified into two, namely, internal factors and external factors (Slameto, 2010). Internal factors are elements that exist in individuals who learn to be physical factors, psychological factors, and fatigue factors. External factors are also factors that influence learning outside the individual, consisting of family factors, school factors, and community factors. The environment is a significant factor in the impact of learning outcomes on students; this educational experience consists of three subjects, namely family, school, and community, which are considered to be the center of education. *Tri Pusat Pendidikan* is a term first coined by Indonesian educational figure Ki Hadjar Dewantara, which means three educational centers consisting of family education, schools, and

community training. (Kurniawan, 2015). The role of family, school, the community is needed in increasing motivation and student learning outcomes because education as a deliberate and planned effort to help the potential and abilities of children is not only the responsibility of the government but also parents, schools, and the community. Here, the family environment that is (father and mother) has the responsibility and plays the role of the most influential educator. The family environment can have a positive influence on children's learning activities if the family conditions are quite harmonious, the economic conditions are sufficient.

The school environment, if the quality of the school environment where many students are successful, will undoubtedly give influence all students to learn well and spur them to compete for results. Meanwhile, the environmental factors of the community did not have a small effect on children's learning outcomes. Indeed some influences cause problems for some students, but some provide a positive impact. In this case, a matter of positive or negative influence will be obtained by students from the environment of the community, depends on how students deal with it. Many writings discuss the function of education but do not yet understand clearly about the environment as the place for training to take place. If an educator cannot interpret that training is only in school, then the family and community will throw the blame entirely on the school if the student experiences immorality. This paper will provide an understanding for every parent and educator about the collaboration of the educational environment in realizing educational goals, through an understanding of the educational center.

Understanding Tri Pusat Pendidikan

The term *Tri Pusat Pendidikan* is a term used by Indonesian education leaders, namely Ki Hajar Dewantara, which describes educational institutions or environments that exist around humans that affect the behavior of students. This subject contains three subjects, namely family education (informal education), education in schools (formal education), and education in society (non-formal culture) (Ahmadi and Uhbiyanti, 1991).

1. Family environment

The family is the first social environment known by a child, so it influences the learning outcomes. Where the child forges himself into the process of growth, it is where the child forms himself into the process of maturation. During this period, each child will imitate attitudes and behaviors as they are examples from their parents as provisions for their adult life. For example, students who have the burden to look for additional costs of family livelihood are generally relatively low learning outcomes because they do not have enough learning time. Vice versa, usually students can achieve better learning outcomes if they have the full time to study at home.

Furthermore, students whose families experience economic difficulties also find it challenging to hold learning facilities so that they become obstacles for students in learning. Logical parents need to demonstrate which actions are right and wrong or bad. Parents display this attitude in such a way that a child can distinguish its behavior in social relationships, both with friends of the same age or when they grow up. Besides, it is essential to be ethical in explaining the basis of every action. In other words, parents must behave based on specific standards, so that they do not act carelessly and give directions. Parents have to create a cozy atmosphere for a child.

2. School Environment

Among the *Tri Pusat Pendidikan*, schools are designed to implement education. The influence of this environment on student learning outcomes is quite significant because school is the other social environment after the family that will be known by students on the government school, including teaching staff, curriculum, learning facilities, and the overall school environment. As a formal educational institution, a school certainly has a programmed learning system. Learning systems that implementing and carried out conscientiously will undoubtedly have a significant impact on the progress of student learning outcomes. Schools should be the center of education to prepare humans as individual citizens, citizens, and citizens of the world in the future. Schools as educational centers are schools that reflect a developed society because of the optimal use of science and technology (Baderiah & Ilham, 2019; Ihsan, 1997). An alternative that might be done following the situation and conditions of the school include: 1) teaching that educates, 2) improvement and stabilization of the implementation of guidance and counseling programs, 3) school library developers become a learning resource center

(PSB), and 4) development and strengthening school management programs, especially those related to students.

3. Community Environment

The community environment is an environment other than family that has a significant effect on student learning outcomes. The environment teaches them many things, especially the ability to interact with other people (hone interpersonal intelligence). The community environment affects children's learning outcomes through the process of interaction with peers and games. When in the community, he gathers with children who like to learn, so he will be affected to learn. Community and education links can be reviewed in 3 aspects, namely as follows: 1) the community as the organizer of education, 2) social institutions and social groups in the city, both directly and indirectly, have an educational role and function, and 3) in the community provided various learning resources (Ihsan, 1997; Ilham, 2020).

The function of the community as a center of education is very dependent on the level of development of the city and the learning resources available in it. The mass media is one factor in an increasingly important role in the community. In general, the mass media has three functions, namely information, education, and recreation. The mass media also has three kinds of influence, namely the effect of socialization in a broad sense, special effects in the short term, and provide education in a more formal sense.

METHODS

The research approach used in this analysis is library review, which is accomplished by compiling articles or scientific journals relating to Tri Pusat Pendidikan, informal education, formal education, non-formal training. This review is qualitative, by analyzing phenomena occurring in Indonesia, trying to formulate problems that occur, and then comparing to the obtained literature. Data collection techniques are carried out by collecting data, in particular information sources, through books, articles, notes, and various other scientific literature in the form of a combined literature review. The data collected are then inductively analyzed to produce grounded theory, a theory that emerges from data and not from hypotheses. (Thomas, David R., 2006) The writing steps in preparing this article are

1. Choosing an issue;
2. a preliminary study;
3. Issue Formulation;
4. Formulating aims;
5. Carrying out the study;
6. Having discussions;
7. Formulate a conclusion made from the results of the analysis and other writers' recommendations.

RESULTS

Role Of Education In Tri Pusat Pendidikan

1. The Role of the Family in Education

Family education or informal education is a familiar path of knowledge. Informal education is a learning process in the nuclear family that takes place in everyday life. Parents will, of course, introduce their kids to the things around them. Parents will teach the names of objects, how to pronounce words politely and correctly, how to eat and drink properly, how to appreciate the right way, how to write, and even how to worship as a basis for children later to enter the formal world (school and community). In principle, education in the family is to help children how to learn well. The family is also the central installation of moral foundations for children, which is usually reflecting on the attitudes and behavior of parents as an example that children can emulate. In this connection, Ki Hajar Dewantara states that:

"A sense of love, a sense of unity and other feelings and mental states that are generally very useful for the ongoing education, especially character education, is found in family life in a strong and pure nature so that no other education centers can match"(Muthoifin and Jinan, 2015).

Children born in the care of parents and raised in the family. Parents without direct rule assume the task as educators, both as carers, as carers, as coaches, and as teachers and leaders of their children. It is the essential task of every human being. Children also suck the norms that exist in family members, both father, and mother and older siblings. Parents in the family are obliged to pay attention to their children and also educate them since they were small, even when the child was still in the womb. So, the

duty of parents to educate their children is entirely independent of their position, expertise, or experience in the field of legal education. In fact, according to Imam Ghazali, "Children are a message from God to their father's mother" (Al-Ghazali, 1995: 257).

Family education is part of the out-of-school education pathway that is held within the family and which provides religious beliefs, cultural values, moral values , and skills. Education is a shared responsibility between family, community, and government. School is only a helper for the continuation of knowledge in the family because the first and foremost education for children is in the family. The transition of forms of knowledge outside the school path to the path of school education (formal) requires "very close cooperation" between parents and school (education).

The philosophy of their parents will mainly influence children's attitudes towards school. Likewise, parents' trust in schools (educators) is very much needed to replace their duties while in the schoolroom. It is imperative to note, given that lately often unfavorable actions are taken by students, while parents do not want to know, even tend to blame the school.

Parents must pay attention to their children's schools, namely by paying attention to their experiences and appreciate all their efforts. Likewise, parents must show their cooperation in directing the way children learn at home, helping to guide their homework, not taking too much time of their children for household chores. Also, parents should try to motivate and guide children in learning.

The role of the family in education is significant in the scientific development and attitudes of a student. It can be seen from the physical factors that show that in a child's body, there can be certain similarities in body shape, although only a little. Then if viewed from psychological factors, many parents' actions and attitudes are consciously or unconsciously imitated by children; this is because parents for children are the first role models seen by children and will become a guide in later life. Especially in the matter of ways of worship and morality, for example, how to perform ablution, prayer, purification, or meet with the environment. The better the quality of the family, the more likely it will be to grow quality children. However, on the contrary, if the quality of the family is terrible, then it is more likely to raise children who are less qualified.

2. The Role of Schools in Education

Schools play an essential role in education because of their enormous influence on the character of the students. Also, the school has a function as an educational center for the personal formation of students. With schools, the government educates its people to become experts following the fields and talents of students, which are useful for themselves and useful for their homeland and nation. Schools are deliberately provided or explicitly built for places of education so that it can be classified as a place or educational institution second after the family, especially schools, also have the function to continue family education, with teachers in exchange for parents who must be obeyed. As a result of the development of technology and parents' limitations on these two things, parents are no longer able to educate their children. To carry out these tasks requires another person who is more expert in the field, in this case, an educator or teacher.

The school conducts education coaching for its students based on the beliefs and demands of the times. Schools as educational institutions have responsibilities (Wentzel 1991) for three factors:

- a. Regular Responsibility School or madrasa as an educational institution according to the function of the task and educational objectives must carry out coaching according to applicable regulations
- b. Scientific Responsibility Schools or madrassas as educational institutions have the responsibility of transferring knowledge to students.
- c. Functional responsibilities of schools or madrasah, in addition to guiding under applicable regulations, schools must also be responsible through educators (teachers) to carry out programs that are structured in the curriculum (Siddik, 2016).

3. The Role of Society in Education

Ki Hajar Dewantara stated the nature of youth because, at that time, the youth movement played a role and had a significant influence. He said:

"Where the youth movement is a big supporter of education, both those that lead to mental intelligence or character and those that lead to social behavior, it is necessary for the youth movement to be recognized as an educational center and included in the education plan."(Kurniawan, 2015).

The community participates in taking responsibility for education. In a pure society can be interpreted as a collection of individuals and groups bound by the unity of the state, culture, and religion. Every nation has certain ideals, regulations, and power systems. The community is very influential in providing direction on children's education, especially community leaders or the authorities in it. When children grow up, they are expected to become useful members of villagers, city residents, and citizens.

Thus, they carry on their shoulders the participation of guiding the growth and development of children. It means that leaders and authorities from the community share responsibility for the administration of education because the burden of learning is essentially the moral responsibility of every adult, both as individuals and as social groups. The community is called the non-formal education environment viewed from the education environment, which provides education intentionally and plans to all its members, but not systematically. Functionally the community accepts all members who are pluralistic (plural) and directs to be a good member of the society for the achievement of social welfare, namely mental and spiritual well-being or physical and physical well-being (Choiri, 2017).

If in educational institutions the educator is a teacher, then in the community the education is adults who are responsible for the maturity of their members through further socialization which are laid down by the family and also the school before they enter the community. Each member with full awareness and responsibility either individually or collectively through the institution or institution they lead (Choiri, 2017). National education is universal, comprehensive, and integrated into the framework of developing the Indonesian nation as a whole are primarily the responsibility of the entire Indonesian nation and are implemented by the family, society, and government. Education is a shared responsibility between family, community, and government with the aim that everyone can own education, according to the abilities of each individual.

DISCUSSION

Cooperation Between Parents, Schools, and Communities in Improving Quality of Education

The educational process carried out by these three environments can be stated as follows. Mentally, the foundations of education are laid down by the household, and academically conceptually developed by the school so that the development of children's education is increasingly directed. How close the integrated cooperation of the three types of the educational environment to bring children to the common goal, namely to form children into good community members for the nation, state, and religion (Wursanto, 1987: 83).

The implementation of education is a shared responsibility between the family, the community, and the government, therefore training lasts for life and is carried out within the family, school, and district. The targets to be achieved from education are the formation of cognitive (mental), affective (mental or moral attitude), and psychomotor (skill/skill) aspects. Ideally, the structure of cognitive aspects becomes the duties and responsibilities of educators (teachers) in schools, the formation of useful elements becomes the tasks and responsibilities of parents, and the establishment of psychomotor aspects becomes the tasks and obligations of the community (course institutions and the like).

With this division of tasks, the problem of education is the responsibility of all parties: parents, educators (teachers), and the community. Moral education, such as religion, manners, ethics, and the like, is the duty and responsibility of parents. Vocational training, such as computer courses, foreign languages, sewing, is the duty and responsibility of the community (course institutions). At the same time, science and technology education (science and technology) is the duty and responsibility of educators (teachers) in schools. However, because not every family can provide the education intended in the family, the school often feels the need to give its responsibility to develop all the abilities of students so that the school often provides content that can be useful for students (not just cognitive). It is necessary to optimize the tri education center To solve social problems, with steps including equal distribution of formal education, the value of formal education, and expanding the role of non-school education (Hidayat and Machali, 2012).

Equitable Education Formal

Although formal education for our society can be said to be equitable, it needs to be reviewed to what extent it can contribute to solving the above social problems. Especially for villages that have

serious social issues, a breakthrough needs to be done by the government by freeing school tuition payments to students who come from these places.

A study conducted by Galloway and Ishimaru that examines the role that formal leaders can play in creating routines and practices to encourage and maintain educational unit leadership from a team of educators, parents, and students who focus on equality in schools that results in an expansion of the concept of leadership from position authority, as well as routines that strengthen the principal as an individual with strength. Furthermore, they highlighted the methods of education units that appeared but were limited to supporting the ongoing involvement of the team with data focused on equity over time to inform sustainable repetitive improvement (Galloway and Ishimaru, 2020). Galloway and Ishimaru conclude that maintaining equality-based improvement work requires an essential role for leaders who focus on social justice in building this routine towards developing the capacity of others in the education unit. The government needs to provide substantial subsidies to areas that are experiencing many social problems so that an increase in the education unit for children will change their mental attitude in the future. In the context of regional autonomy, regional governments can use local policies to pay attention to their regions and provide substantial subsidies to areas or villages that are experiencing social problems.

Charge Value in Formal Education

The value of values informal education is very often heard, often even polemic, whether it becomes a separate subject or integrated into other disciplines. With the concept of the 2013 curriculum, it is possible to include content values in existing issues, the expected character values are directed towards religious morals shown by students (Ilham, 2020). Students who have noble character will be reflected in the behavior displayed in social life. Education is tasked with preparing children to face tomorrow (Nuridin, 2020; Santaria et al. 2016). Thus, learning should be following the needs of future children when they enter the community. School is obliged to instill the knowledge, skills, and attitudes that individuals need in navigating their lives in society. So that education in the fields of study is also responsible for developing that ability. Often there is a dichotomy or mutual blame about the value education, whether it is given at school or in the family/community. The school considers the value of knowledge in the family because most of the time, students are at home (not at school), during the parents or the community view. After all, the school assignments also educate the affective and psychomotor aspects of moral and religious lessons, and then mistakes are often delegated to the school.

Value education is the responsibility of all as a function of the tri education center, so there is no need for a dichotomy; all parties must unite to provide value education to children or students. Even though knowledge is the goal of education, students' competency is a top priority as a provision in the future (Mirick et al., 2016). One of the skills that must be owned by students is sourced from religious education, which is the most significant foundation for forming the character of students so that they have sufficient moral competence to develop a good personality. Thus failure in family education (if it occurs) can be compensated by giving a load of values on formal education.

Increasing the Role of Education Outside School

Out-of-School Education (PLS) is a strategic education to solve social problems, but the government has not provided a sufficient portion to play a role lately. In the era of regional autonomy, the government needs to mobilize non-formal education further to be able to help solve these social problems. The local government knows more about the condition of the region than the central government so that it has more appropriate policies on how to solve social issues experienced by several areas. Non-formal education that only relies on outdated issues such as chasing package A, B or completing illiteracy needs to be reduced but needs to increase or increase activities on problems (1) improving the quality of women's education programs and parent education, (2) expanding equity and improvement of the quality of continuing education through courses coaching programs, business study groups, internships, and training scholarships.

They are continuing Education Program, consisting of (1) programs oriented to the provision of personal development and professionalism through courses that meet the needs of citizens, such as services, language, agriculture, household, health, engineering and encroachment, sports arts, crafts, and industry, as well as specialized skills; (2) programs oriented to the provision of provisions to work

for a living to improve the welfare of life through the Chase Business program, Internships, Scholarships / Courses; (3) provision-oriented plans for continuing higher education, which is carried out through the SME Equivalent Package C program which is integrated with skills training so that an increase in livelihood skills accompanies an increase in knowledge. Improving the quality of continuing education in problem areas will have a tremendous economic impact so that poverty will gradually be reduced in problem areas. Providing skills will provide a conducive space for additional family income, and with the presence of business activities, lousy behavior such as gambling, alcohol can be reduced.

CONCLUSION

Tri Pusat Pendidikan is three essential elements that play a crucial role in education and become the center of educational activities. This theme covers three subjects, namely family education (informal learning), school education (formal education), and social education (non-formal culture). The concept of an educational center has the meaning of education in educational institutions (schools), community training, and family knowledge. All three are often referred to as the educational/social environment of students, where education takes place in these three environments. This concept implies that learning can be achieved wherever and whenever and becomes a shared responsibility. This concept tells us that the community and family have a balanced responsibility for the success of the prosecutors of knowledge. That is, it is not only schools that are made and mandated as institutions that have great (full) responsibility for the success or not only individuals in their education process. Therefore it is expected that between the three tri education centers can work together in achieving optimal learning outcomes. Because in essence, the role of the *Tri Pusat Pendidikan* always jointly influences humans, even though the weight of influence varies throughout human life. As a result of the times and the limitations of parents in educating children, educational activities are also carried out in an institution called a school or madrasa. Education that is done at school or madrasa is called formal education. Society is a place or element that plays an essential role in education. The community education environment is called non-formal training.

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